

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Cheksiz izotropik fazoda qalin sferik qobiqdan nostatsionar to‘lqinlar

T.B.Ashurov, X.O.Musurmonov, M.O.Musurmonova, A.M.Shukurov

Qarshi davlat universiteti, Qarshi, O‘zbekiston
Qarshi davlat texnika universiteti, Qarshi, O‘zbekiston
Shaxrisabz davlat pedagogika instituti, Shaxrisabz, O‘zbekiston

Kirish. Tutash muhitlarda nostatsionar to‘lqin jarayonlarini matematik modellashtirish va o‘rganish to‘lqinlar dinamikasining murakkab, shu bilan birga dolzarb muammolaridandir. To‘lqinlar dinamikasi muammolarining dolzarbligi muhandislikning turli sohalarida dinamik kuchlar ta’siri ostida ishlaydigan yangi konstruksiyalarini yaratilishi, shuningdek, geofizika, seysmologiya, konchilik sanoati, fuqarolik va sanoat qurilishidan kelib chiqadigan amaliy muammolar bilan aniqlanadi.

Hozirgi vaqtda uzluksiz muhitlarda to‘lqinlarning tarqalishi va difraksiyasini o‘rganishga bag‘ishlangan juda ko‘p sondagi ilmiy tadqiqot ishlari mavjud. Masalan, [1] da suyuqlik va qattiq jismlardagi zarba to‘lqini jarayonlarini modellashtirishning ucho‘lchovli uslubiyoti, shuningdek, suyuqlik va konstruksiyalarning o‘zaro ta’sirini modellashtirish masalalari o‘rganilgan. [2] da esa sirtlarga normal tipdagi zarbalar paytida aylanma yupqa qobiqlarida paydo bo‘ladigan elliptik chegaraviy qatlami uchun chegara masalaning yechish usuli ishlab chiqilgan. Maqolada elliptik chegaraviy qatlami tenglamalarini yechish usuli eksponensial formadagi Laplas yechimining tasvirlarining asimptotik shakldan foydalanishga asoslangan hamda sharsimon qobiq holi uchun olingan analitik yechimlar asosida normal kuchlanishning sonli natijalari olingan.

Elastik yarim fazoda sferik bo‘shliqdan nostatsionar ko‘ndalang siljish to‘lqinlarining tarqalishi [3] tadqiqotda o‘rganilgan. Ko‘chish vektori va kuchlanish tenzorining komponentlari uchun formulalar olingan. [4] maqolada tekisliklar bilan chegaralangan ideal suyuqliklar qatlamida sferik bo‘shliqdan nostatsionar to‘lqin tarqalishining o‘qsimetrik masalasi qaralgan. Laplas tasvir fazosida masala cheksiz matritsali tenglamani yechishga keltirilgan. Sonli natijalar sferik bo‘shliq yaqinida bosim o‘zgarishi grafiklar shaklida tasvirlangan.

[5] da yassi seysmik to‘lqinning ko‘ndalang tushishi natijasida yuzaga kelgan yer osti quvurining statsionar tebranishlari o‘rganilgan. Qiya to‘lqinni quvur bo‘ylab yuqori tezlikda tarqaladigan bir nechta bo‘ylama va ko‘ndalang to‘lqinlar shaklida ifodalanishi mumkinligi ko‘rsatilgan. Maqola [6] qalin devorli sferik qobiqdan elastik fazoda kososimmetrik ko‘ndalang siljish to‘lqinlarining tarqalishi masalasiga bag‘ishlangan. O‘lchovsiz vaqtga nisbatan integral Laplas almashtirishi qo‘llanilgan. Fazoda siljish vektori va kuchlanish tenzorining komponentlari uchun formulalar olingan. Originalga o‘tish qoldiq nazariyasi yordamida amalga oshirilgan. Sonli tajribalar o‘tkazilgan. [7] maqolada izotropik sferik qatlamda kososimmetrik ko‘ndalang to‘lqinlarning tarqalishi masalasi ko‘rib chiqilgan. O‘lchovsiz vaqtga nisbatan integral Laplas almashtirishi va o‘zgaruvchilarni to‘liq bo‘lmagan ajratish usuli qo‘llanilgan. Ko‘chish vektori va kuchlanish tenzorining komponentlari uchun formulalar olinadi. Sonli tajribalar natijalari grafiklar shaklida berilgan.

Ushbu maqola chegaralanmagan izotropik fazoda qalin sferik qobiqdan nostatsionar bo‘ylama to‘lqin tarqalishi haqidagi masalani o‘rganishga bag‘ishlangan. Ishning maqsadi va vazifasi – masalaning yechish algoritmini ishlab chiqish va sonli eksperimentlar asosida qobiq hamda atrof muhitda nostatsionar to‘lqin jarayonlarini tahlil etishdan iboratdir.

Masalaning qo‘yilishi. Aytaylik, cheksiz bir jinsli izotropik fazoda deformatsiyalanuvchi sferik qobiq joylashgan bo‘lib, u ichki va tashqi tomondan radiuslari mos ravishda r_1 va r_2 ($r_1 < r_2$) bo‘lgan sferik sirtlar bilan chegaralangan (rasm 1). Muhit qobiq va harakatini o‘rganish uchun boshlang‘ich nuqtasi O qobiq markazida bo‘lgan (r, θ, ϑ) sferik koordinatalar sistemasini kiritilgan.

Vaqtning $\tau = 0$ paytida sferik qobiq ichki sirtiga tekis taqsimlangan normal $p_1(\tau, \theta)$ sirt kuchi ta’sir etadi. Natijada qobiq va atrof muhitda faqat nostatsionar bo‘ylama to‘lqin tarqaladi.

Masalaning o‘qsimmetrik ekanligini e’tiborga olib, muhit va qobiq harakati ko‘chish ϕ_k potentsiallariga nisbatan to‘lqin tenglamalari orqali tasvirlanadi ($k = 0, 1$; indeks “0” muhitni, “1” indeks esa sferik qobiqni bildiradi, nuqtalar bilan vaqtga bo‘yicha differentsiallash belgilangan):

$$\gamma_k^2 \ddot{\phi}_k = \Delta \phi_k \quad (1)$$

bu yerda Δ - sferik koordinatalar sistemasida Laplas operatori.

Rasm 1.

Boshlang‘ich shartlar – bir jinsli:

$$\phi_k|_{\tau=0} = \dot{\phi}_k|_{\tau=0} = 0. \quad (2)$$

Cheksizlikda esa to‘lqin so‘nadi:

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} \phi_0 = 0 \quad (3)$$

Sferik qobiq ichki sirtida chegaraviy shart

$$\sigma_{rr}^{(1)}|_{r=r_2} = p_1(\tau, \theta) \quad (4)$$

ko'rinishga ega.

Sferik qobiq bilan atrof muhit o'rtasidagi kontakt shartlar

$$\sigma_{rr}^{(1)}|_{r=r_2} = \sigma_{rr}^{(0)}|_{r=r_2}, \quad w_0|_{r=r_2} = w_1|_{r=r_2} \quad (5)$$

tengliklar bilan ifodalanadi. Bu yerda w_k va $\sigma_{rr}^{(k)}$ lar ($k = 0, 1$) mos ravishda muhit va qobiqning kuchlanish-deformatsiya holati komponentalari.

Ko'chish ϕ_k potentsiallari $w_k, \sigma_{rr}^{(k)}, \sigma_{\theta\theta}^{(k)}$ muhit va qobiqning kuchlanish-deformatsiya holati komponentalari bilan o'zaro quyidagi

$$w_k = \frac{\partial \phi_k}{\partial r}, \quad \sigma_{rr}^{(k)} = \frac{\partial w_k}{\partial r} + 2\chi_k \frac{w_k}{r}, \quad \sigma_{\theta\theta}^{(k)} = \chi_k \sigma_{rr}^{(k)} + (1 + \chi_k - 2\chi_k^2) w_k / r, \quad (6)$$

munosabatlar orqali bog'langan.

Yechish metodi. Masalani yechish uchun o'lchovsiz vaqtga nisbatan integral Laplas integral almashtirishlari [8] va o'zgaruvchilarni to'liq bo'lmagan ajratish usuli qo'llanilgan.

Tasvirlar fazosida berilgan va noma'lum funksiyalar Lejandr ortogonal ko'phadlari [9] bo'yicha cheksiz qatorlarga yoyilib, masala qatorlar koeffitsiyentlariga nisbatan cheksiz algebraik tenglamalar sistemasiga keltirilgan va u ikki matritsa tenglama ko'rinishda yozilgan. Sistemaning yechimi eksponentialar bo'yicha cheksiz qatorlar ko'rinishida izlanib, bu qatorlar koeffitsientlarga nisbatan rekurrent munosabatlar va boshlang'ich shartlar olingan. Bu munosabatlar qatorlar koeffitsientlari va izlanayotgan yechimni Laplas almashtirishlari parametrining ratsional funksiyalari ko'rinishda aniqlashga va ularning tasvirlaridan originalga o'tishda qoldiqlar nazariyasidan foydalanish imkonini beradi [10].

Tasvir fazosida kuchlanish tenzori va ko'chish vektori komponentalari uchun formulalar olingan.

$$w_{1n}^L(r, s) = -r^{-n-2} (\gamma_1 s)^{-n} D_{n1}(r\gamma_1 s), \quad \sigma_{rrn}^{(1)L}(r, s) = r^{-n-3} (\gamma_1 s)^{-n} \beta_1 W_{n1}(r\gamma_1 s),$$

$$w_{0n}^L(r, s) = -\frac{R_{n1}(\zeta) e^{-\zeta} e^z}{r^2 \zeta^n R_{n1}(z)} D_{n1}(r_2 \gamma_1 s), \quad \sigma_{rrn}^{(0)L}(r, s) = \frac{\beta_0 Q_{n1}(\zeta) e^{-\zeta} e^z}{r^3 \zeta^n r_2^2 Q_{n1}(z)} W_{n1}(r_2 \gamma_1 s).$$

$$D_{n1}(\xi) = \sum_{i,j=0}^{\infty} \left[R_{n1}(\xi) a_{ij}^{(n)}(s) e^{-\xi} + (-1)^n G_{n1}(\xi) b_{ij}^{(n)}(s) \right] x^i y^{-j-1},$$

$$W_{n1}(\xi) = \sum_{i,j=0}^{\infty} \left[Q_{n1}(\xi) a_{ij}^{(n)}(s) e^{-\xi} + (-1)^n E_{n1}(\xi) b_{ij}^{(n)}(s) \right] x^i y^{-j-1}.$$

Sonli natijalar. Sonli eksperiment natijalari cheksiz granit ($E_0 = 5 \cdot 10^{10}$ Pa, $\nu_0 = 0.15$, $\rho_0 = 3000$ kg/m³) fazoda ichki va tashqi radiuslar mos ravishda $r_1 = 1.0$, $r_2 = 2.5$ bo'lgan qalin po'lat ($E_1 = 20.1 \cdot 10^{10}$ Pa, $\nu_1 = 0.3$, $\rho_1 = 7800$ kg/m³) sferik qobiqdan nostatsionar bo'yлама to'lqin tarqalishi jarayoni uchun olingan. U holda o'lchovsiz parametrlar $\gamma_0 = 0.71$, $\gamma_1 = 1.0$, $\chi_0 = 0.1765$, $\chi_1 = 0.43$ qiymatlar bilan aniqlanadi. Qobiq ichki sirtiga esa $p_1(\tau, \theta) = f(\tau)H(\tau)$, $f(\tau) = p_0$, $p_0 = 1$ normal kuch ta'sir etadi.

Quyidagi 2 va 3-raslarda qobiqning kuchlanish $\sigma_{rr}^{(1)}$, $\sigma_{\theta\theta}^{(1)}$ komponentalarining vaqt bo'yicha o'zgarishi grafiklari tasvirlangan. Bu yerda $r = 1.2$ (egri chiziq 1), $r = 1.5$ (egri chiziq 2) va $r = 1.8$ (egri chiziq 3).

Rasm 2.

Xulosa. Cheksiz bir jinsli izotropik fazoda joylashgan qalin sferik qobiqdan nostatsionar bo'ylama to'lqin tarqalishi masalasining yechish algoritmi ishlab chiqildi. Sonli natijalar olindi va ular grafiklar shaklda tasvirlangan. Sonli eksperimentlarning natijalarini geofizika, seysmologiya va yer osti inshootlari hamda omborlarini loyihalashtirishda foydalanish mumkin.

Rasm 3.

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